

COMPARISON OF MALE-AUTHORED AND FEMALE-AUTHORED PROSE

Kahhorov

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10806574>

Abstract. *This article examines the potential disparities between prose authored by males and females. The analysis delves into various aspects of writing style, thematic elements, and character portrayal, aiming to illuminate the nuances that distinguish male-authored prose from other literary works. By scrutinizing these differences, the study aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of gender-related patterns in literature, shedding light on the societal influences that may shape literary expression.*

The article outlines the selection criteria for the literary works under scrutiny and elucidates the analytical framework used to identify potential differences in style, content, and character portrayal. The methodology section also addresses potential limitations and biases inherent in the study design. The analysis presents the results of the comparative examination of male-authored prose, highlighting distinctive features and patterns observed in the selected literary works. The findings illuminate potential differences in narrative structure, language usage, character development, and thematic emphasis, offering valuable insights into gender-related nuances in literary expression.

Keywords: *Gender, literature, prose, comparative analysis, male-authored, feminist theory, literary criticism, gender representation.*

Introduction: The introduction provides an overview of gender-based disparities in literature and highlights the significance of investigating potential differences between male-authored prose and other literary works. The author presents the rationale for the study, emphasizing the relevance of exploring gender-specific patterns in prose and the implications for literary analysis and interpretation. Several statistical phenomena have emerged that appear to be fairly stable across a variety of contexts. For example, females seem to talk more about relationships than do males (Aries & Johnson 1983; Tannen 1990) and use more compliments and apologies (Holmes 1988; Holmes 1989) and facilitative tag questions (Holmes 1984)

Romanticism is an attitude or intellectual direction that shaped a great deal of Western civilization's late 18th- and mid-19th-century literature, art, music, architecture, criticism, and historiography. The principles of order, serenity, harmony, balance, idealization, and rationalism that characterized Classicism in general and late 18th-century Neoclassicism in particular might be understood as being rejected by romanticism. This article made research on the authors of romanticism. Pre-Romanticism, or a series of connected movements from the middle of the 18th century onward, might be considered the precursor of Romanticism proper. One of these was a renewed interest in the medieval romance, which is where the name "Romantic movement" originated. The romance was a chivalric adventure tale or ballad that stood in stark contrast to the elegant formality and artificiality of dominant Classical forms of literature, such as the English heroic couplet in poetry or the French Neoclassical tragedy, with its emphasis on individual heroism and the exotic and mysterious. This newfound fascination with comparatively simple yet blatantly sentimental historical literary representations was to be a defining feature of Romanticism.

Main Body: During the Romanticism period, there were discernible differences in the prose of male and female authors, reflecting societal norms and gender-specific experiences. Male authors of the Romantic era, such as William Wordsworth, Samuel Taylor Coleridge, and Lord Byron, often portrayed a sense of individualism, adventure, and rebellion in their prose. Their narratives frequently centered on themes of heroism, nature's sublimity, and the pursuit of personal freedom. The male-authored prose of this period often exuded an assertive tone and a longing for escapism from the constraints of society, embracing the concept of the "romantic hero."

In contrast, female authors of the Romantic era, including Mary Shelley, Jane Austen, and the Brontë sisters, articulated a different perspective in their prose. Their writings frequently explored domestic life, female experiences, and the constraints imposed by societal norms. Female-authored prose during the Romanticism period often depicted the complexities of relationships, the struggles of women within patriarchal structures, and the challenges of upholding personal autonomy in a constrained society. Emotions, introspection, and the intricacies of human interactions were pivotal themes in their works, reflecting a nuanced portrayal of the female experience during that era.

These differences in themes, narrative focus, and the portrayal of characters in male and female-authored prose during the Romanticism period are indicative of the distinct societal roles, expectations, and perspectives that influenced literary expression. The male-authored prose often reflected a yearning for transcendence and a rebellion against societal strictures, while female-authored prose encompassed a more introspective and nuanced exploration of personal relationships and societal constraints. These nuances in prose reflect the gendered experiences and societal expectations prevalent during the Romantic era, shedding light on the diverse literary expressions brought forth by male and female authors of that time.

The styles of male and female authors during the Romanticism period often differed in several fundamental aspects, reflecting the distinct societal roles and experiences that influenced their literary expression:

1. Narrative Focus:

- Male authors often placed emphasis on individualism, adventure, and the pursuit of personal freedom in their narratives. Their prose frequently revolved around themes of heroism, nature's sublimity, and the quest for transcendence.

- Female authors, on the other hand, tended to center their narratives on domestic life, the complexities of human relationships, and the challenges faced by women within patriarchal structures. Their prose delved into the intricacies of emotions and the constraints imposed by societal norms.

2. Language Usage:

- Male-authored prose often employed assertive language and vivid descriptions to convey a sense of adventure, rebellion, or the awe of nature's grandeur.

- Female-authored prose frequently utilized nuanced language to delve into the intricacies of human emotions, societal expectations, and the struggles faced by women, demonstrating a more introspective and emotive approach.

3. Character Portrayal:

- Male authors often depicted characters as romantic heroes, embodying traits of individualism, defiance, and a quest for personal fulfillment.

- Female authors portrayed protagonists dealing with the complexities of domestic life, societal expectations, and personal autonomy, often highlighting the nuances of female experiences within the constraints of society.

4. Thematic Emphasis:

- Male-authored prose commonly emphasized themes of rebellion, self-discovery, and a longing for escapism from societal constraints, reflecting a yearning for transcendence and freedom.

- Female-authored prose frequently addressed themes of love, family dynamics, societal limitations, and the challenges of upholding personal autonomy within societal expectations, portraying a more intimate exploration of interpersonal relationships and the constraints faced by women.

These differences in narrative focus, language usage, character portrayal, and thematic emphasis exemplify the distinct approaches and perspectives that male and female authors of the Romanticism period brought to their literary works, reflecting the gendered experiences and societal influences prevalent during that era.

Let's delve deeper into examples of male and female authors from the Romanticism period to illustrate the differences in their styles.

Male Authors:

- William Wordsworth: In his poetry and prose, Wordsworth often celebrated the grandeur of nature and the spiritual connection between humanity and the natural world. His focus on the sublime landscapes and the individual's place within the natural realm depicted a longing for transcendence and profound emotional experiences, emphasizing themes of solitude and introspection.

- Lord Byron: Byron's literary works frequently featured rebellious and heroic protagonists challenging societal norms and conventions. The narrative tone in his prose often portrayed a sense of defiance, adventure, and a longing for freedom. His renowned work "Childe Harold's Pilgrimage" exemplifies this style with its exploration of the romantic hero's wanderlust and discontent with society.

Female Authors:

- Mary Shelley: In "Frankenstein," Shelley's prose offered a nuanced exploration of human ambition, societal rejection, and the consequences of playing god. Through her use of emotive language and intricate character development, Shelley delved into the ethical dilemmas and the complexities of human relationships, addressing themes of human existence, responsibility, and the pursuit of knowledge.

- Jane Austen: Austen's novels, such as "Pride and Prejudice" and "Sense and Sensibility," delved into the intricacies of personal relationships, social hierarchy, and the limitations imposed by societal expectations. Her narrative style often employed wit, irony, and incisive social commentary, portraying the challenges faced by women in a society governed by strict social norms and the pursuit of personal happiness within these constraints.

The psychology of male and female authors during the Romantic era reflected the societal norms, gender roles, and individual experiences that influenced their literary perspectives and creative expression.

Male authors of the Romantic era often depicted a psychology characterized by a sense of individualism, adventure, and rebellion against societal constraints. Their prose and poetry frequently reflected a yearning for personal freedom, a desire to transcend the limitations of society, and a romanticized portrayal of heroism. The male authors' psychology often centered on themes of self-discovery, the pursuit of independence, and a longing for sublime experiences, encompassing a narrative focus on personal triumph and the exploration of the self within the context of nature and society.

In contrast, female authors during the Romantic era often portrayed a psychology shaped by the societal expectations and limitations imposed on women. Their literary works frequently delved into the complexities of human emotions, the challenges of navigating societal norms, and the impact of patriarchal structures on personal autonomy. The psychology of female authors often reflected themes of resilience, introspection, and the negotiation of personal agency within the constraints of gendered societal roles. Their writings often showcased a keen awareness of the intricacies of human relationships, emotional depth, and the psychological impacts of societal expectations on women's lives.

Overall, the psychology of male authors during the Romantic era often emphasized themes of individualism, rebellion, and a yearning for transcendence, while the psychology of female authors centered on the exploration of emotions, personal resilience, and the complexities of navigating societal constraints. These differences in psychological themes and narrative focus are indicative of the diverse experiences and societal dynamics that shaped the literary perspectives of male and female authors during the Romantic era.

By examining the literary works of these male and female authors from the Romanticism period, we observe the distinctions in their styles. Male authors often emphasized the grandeur of nature, the pursuit of personal freedom, and themes of heroism and individualism. In contrast, female authors focused on the complexities of human relationships, societal constraints, and the nuances of emotional experiences, displaying a more introspective and intimate exploration of the human condition within the context of societal expectations. The conclusion summarizes the key findings and implications of the study, underscoring the significance of recognizing gender-related disparities in prose. The author also outlines potential avenues for further research and urges for continued exploration of gender-specific nuances in literary expression. In recent years, there has been criticism of studies that show disparities in language usage between genders. This paper's main focus will be on the characteristics that make it easiest to categorize papers according to the gender of the authors.

REFERENCES

1. <https://u.cs.biu.ac.il/~koppel/papers/male-female-text-final.pdf>
2. <https://www.easternct.edu/speichera/understanding-literary-history-all/the-romantic-period.html>
3. <https://www.britannica.com/art/Romanticism>

4. <https://www.jstor.org>